

Barberetta aurea

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Importance:

Barberetta is a sister genus to *Wachendorfia*. A genome assembly of *B. aurea* from Karkloof (KZN) revealed the same supergene locus as *Wachendorfia paniculata*, while analyses of a Ngeli (KZN) population show substantial genetic differences. A long-read assembly of *B. aurea* from Ngeli will help define the boundaries of the supergene locus and clarify whether *Barberetta* comprises multiple species.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 67.72 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 10.5 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm
Genome Length: 0.48 Gigabases
BUSCO completeness score: 99.8% [Single: 86.8%, Duplicated: 12.9%]
BUSCO database: viridiplantae
Assembly N50: 13 849.88 kilobases
Contig number: 2 386

Sample Contributor contact details:

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Group: Monocot

Size: 0.2 – 0.5m.

Distribution:

From Pondoland to north of Pietermaritzburg.